

Concept of Ideal Business & Its Realization Using E-Business Model

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Abstract: In this paper, an attempt is made to identify some of the important characteristics of an Ideal Business in terms of input conditions, system requirements, output conditions and market requirements are identified and analyzed. The paper describes how these characteristics can be achieved in practical business by incorporating electronic online business model using mobile devices called mobile business. The paper also discusses how a small business planned by an entrepreneur can be improved towards an ideal business level by incorporating information communication technology (ICT) components. The conceptual nature of mobile business including major features, value chain, benefits of mobile business from customer's point of view and comparison of mobile business properties with that of ideal business properties are discussed. The various factors affecting mobile business in terms of the characteristics of Ideal business are studied. Finally, some of the possible products and services which can lead to the concept of Ideal Business are identified and analyzed.

Keywords: Ideal Business; E-business; e-business models; e-business strategies; online business

1. Introduction

The word 'Ideal system' refers to the system which has ideal characteristics i.e., perfect in every way. It is what the mind pictures as being perfect. The concept of ideal engine, ideal switch, ideal semiconductor devices like ideal diodes, transistors, etc. have been defined and taken as standards to improve the quality and performance of such practical devices or systems. It is found that, by keeping such hypothetical device or systems in mind, researchers have continuously improve the characteristics/properties of practical devices / systems to upgrade their performances. Hence ideal properties of a device or a system can be used to upgrade or improve its properties towards reaching 100% efficiency. By comparing the properties/characteristics of a practical device/system with its ideal counterpart, one can find out the possible improvements and modifications in that device /system towards reaching the objective of achieving such an ideal device. The model of ideal education system is proposed by identifying its characteristics under Input conditions, Systems requirements, Output conditions and Environmental & social conditions. These characteristics are analyzed with an objective to achieve the goal and the possibility of realizing Ideal Education System through Online Education using E-education model is discussed [1]. The simple definition of Business is a system of doing things with a profit motivation. This includes selling and/or purchasing any products/services with an objective of usually long term profit. A sustainable successful business involves 'Ease of Use'.

2. Properties of Ideal Business

An Ideal business system shall have characteristics which can be predicted and classified. Based on various factors which decides the ideal business system characteristics, a model consisting of the input conditions, output conditions, market conditions and system requirements, is derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method [2, 3]. The block diagram of such a system is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Classifications of Ideal Business Properties

A. Market Conditions

- 1) The Ideal Business sells its products/services to the entire world rather than a single neighborhood and hence it has an unlimited global market.
- 2) The Ideal Business offers a product/service, which enjoys an inelastic demand in the market. (inelastic refers to a product that people need or desire almost at any price.)
- 3) The Ideal Business markets a product/service that cannot be easily copied. This means that the product/service is an original or, at least, it is something that can be copyrighted or patented.

B. Input Conditions

- 1) The Ideal Business has minimal labor requirements. The fewer personnel, the better is the business.
- 2) The Ideal Business operates on a low overhead. It does not need an expensive location. It does not need large amounts of electricity, or advertising, or legal advice, or high-priced employees, or a large inventory.
- 3) The Ideal Business does not require big cash outlays or major investments in equipment or product. In other words, it does not require huge capital.

C. System Requirements

- 1) The Ideal Business is relatively free of all kinds of government regulations or restrictions.
- 2) The Ideal Business is portable or easily moveable. This means one can shift his business and himself anywhere he wants to.

- 3) The Ideal Business satisfies its owner's intellectual needs. There is nothing like being fascinated with what he does.
- 4) The Ideal Business leaves enough free time to its owner. In other words, it doesn't require his labor and attention of 12, 16, or 18 hours a day.
- 5) The Ideal Business is one in which the income is not limited by personal output (Leverage). In the Ideal-Business, one can have 10,000 customers as easily as can have one."
- 6) The ideal Business will not have any liability after sales.
- 7) The ideal Business will not have problems like seasonality, perishability and price drop.

D. Output Conditions

- 1) In ideal Business the demand is always very high than supply and the efficiency of production is always 100%.
- 2) The ideal Business will be sustainable for long time.

Any business which has the above properties is considered as ideal business and the conventional business called brick and mortar business has serious drawbacks/limitations in terms of the above properties.

3. Analysis of Ideal Business Characteristics

Ideal business characteristics can be explained based on their effectiveness in improving the revenue and creating value to the stakeholders. The characteristics mentioned in ideal business model are depicted in figures 2 - 5 and further discussed below:

Figure 2: Input condition characteristics of Ideal business

A. Input Conditions

(1) Minimal labor requirements

One of the strategies followed in any business is low cost strategy. Automation of various processes decreases the need of labours and hence the cost of doing the business. Automation also improves the productivity and most of the time decreases the wastage. Maintaining good labour relationship and improving the productivity is a challenge for personnel department of any organization. Organizations are spending huge amount of their expenditure or profit for labour welfare. The Ideal Business need minimal labor requirements, thus the expenditure for maintaining labour and for their welfare activities is minimized. Hence fewer the personnel, better is the business. An improved business model always use better technology to decrease labour cost.

(2) Low overhead expenditure:

Many of the conventional business firms face challenges due to huge investment requirement on choosing suitable location to en-cash location advantage, to gather required resources uninterruptedly, to maintain skilled employees, to

maintain suitable inventory, to get legal advice to maintain Govt., environmental, International business regulation and proper industrial relations, advertisement in different media and transportation & distribution costs. These investments along with interest and maintenance cost is an impediment in becoming cost leader and in formulating pricing strategy. On other hand, the Ideal Business model will have business features such as it operates on a low overhead. It does not need an expensive location. It does not need large amounts of electricity, or advertising, or legal advice, or high-priced employees, or a large inventory.

(3) No major investments in the form of Capital:

One of the impediments of starting business in practice is gathering capital resource. This involves the cost in creation of production/service facility and cost of gathering all resources in order to do the business. Due to enhanced price/cost of land, buildings, machines and skilled human resources, a business need huge capital investment. Such investment is a remarkable burden for new entrants and the cost involved in such capital investment, raises the level of the break-even point to get the profit. Ideal business should have features in such a way that it does not require big cash outlays or major investments in equipment or product. In other words, it does not require huge capital.

Figure 3: Output condition characteristics of Ideal business

B. Output Conditions

(1) Demand is always higher than supply:

One of the challenges for present managers of business firms is creating demand for their products/services through formulating proper marketing strategy along with adding unlimited value through product/service differentiation. If the demand for a firm's product is equal or higher than its supply capacity, the firm can enjoy sustainable business and profit for long time. To maintain supply close/equal to demand, the firm should enhance its productivity close to 100%. Ideal business model has product/services in such a way that the demand is always higher than supply and the efficiency of production is always 100%.

(2) Sustainability for long time:

If a business firm has products/services and the business model in such a way that it maintains global demand, high efficiency of production to supply close to 100%, consumes less resources for its business functions and adds unbeatable value to its products/service in customers frame of reference, will sustain for long period. Hence according to the definition, an ideal business model will be sustainable for long period.

C. Market Conditions

(1) Unlimited global market

Products/services built/developed as per global standard, creates demand from entire world. Based on either license/patent protection or through blue ocean strategy, a firm can create global demand for its products/services.

Through a proper business model and strategy a firm can sell its products/services to entire globe. To realize unlimited global market a firm also use suitable technology and tangible or intangible product/service along with perishable or non-perishable resources. Hence Ideal Business should sell its products/services to the entire world rather than a single neighborhood and maintains unlimited global market.

(2) Inelastic demand for products/services

A product or service developed for everybody from children to old aged people, for poor to rich, for any genders, with some attractive features for everybody will create inelastic demand in global market. A business model can be called as ideal only if it can decrease the distribution cost, distribution time, advertisement cost and production cost to minimum level close to zero will support the product/service to achieve inelastic demand. A product/service which shows very attractive feature and attracts all segments of global customers like a killer application so that global customers desires to have it at any price creates inelastic demand.

Figure 4: Market condition characteristics of Ideal business

(3) Business protection through copyright or patent

In ideal business model, the products or services of a firm are created in such a way that they should not become obsolete due to any reasons like changes in technology, development of superior product or copying such products or services from competitive firms. The firm should enjoy long term sustainable benefit and profit through some assured protection for its unique products/services without any fear. Hence ideal business model markets a product/service that cannot be easily copied. This means that the product/service is an original or, at least, it is something that can be copyrighted or patented.

D. System Requirements

(1) Free from government regulations or restrictions:

The factors of production like location, investment, resources, technology, inventory, & transportation and the factors of marketing like advertisement, dealer network, niche market, for a business model should be free from country origin of that firm and the country of the customers. The Ideal Business uses its products/services in such a way that its business model is relatively free from all kinds of government regulations or restrictions.

(2) Portability of business to anywhere:

A good business model should have characteristics to run the business location independent. The business should have same level of difficulty and performance in terms of productivity, efficiency, effectiveness and hence revenue and profit even if it is performed any corner of the world irrespective of its location and physical, geographical,

political, economical and technical environment. The Ideal Business should be perfectly portable or easily moveable from one location to other location based on interest of its owner and should have same level of difficulty everywhere. This means one can shift his business and himself anywhere he wants to.

(3) Satisfies owner’s intellectual needs:

Any business model should have critical elements which should be challenging and complex in such a way that only intelligent people should able to crack and become successful. Everybody with any level of intellectual and smartness are not able to reach all the properties of ideal business due to complexity and high intelligence needs of developing features of such models. Being the owner of the business, he should develop and implement ideas suitable to reach ideal business characteristics. The Ideal Business model developed should satisfies its owner’s intellectual needs and there is nothing like being fascinated with what he does.

(4) Enough free time to its owner & employees

One of the characteristics of ideal business model is automation at all levels. The business processes and elements should be designed in such a way that the required resources should be used in minimum extent so as the time of the owner, managers and the labours. This kind of automation in all activities of the business maintains quality but eliminates hard work by owner & employees without effecting the quality of the product or customer service. Hence Ideal Business model leaves enough free time to its owner/employees. In other words, it doesn’t require his labor and attention of 12, 16, or 18 hours a day.

(5) Income is not limited by personal output (Leverage):

In many business models the productivity and hence the profit depends on the personal output (Leverage) of its human resources. Based on training and boosting employee morale organizations are trying to enhance their productivity and hence the profit. Ideal business model should have features like level of automation and duplication of products/services in such a way that it should fulfill global demand without requirement of additional resources. All the essential properties of business like production, distribution, marketing, customer support etc. should not limited by personal output or leverage of the organization and hence the income is independent on the personal outcome. The business firm should able to provide same kind and level of service to its customers irrespective of their numbers. Hence the Ideal Business model is one in which the income is not limited by personal output (Leverage). In the Ideal-Business, one can have 10,000 customers as easily as can have one.”

Figure 5: System condition characteristics of Ideal business

(6) No liability after sales:

One of the challenges for business firms is after sales support. Firms should design and develop their products/services in such a way to minimize the problem of after sales. Based on the chosen product/service, its features, and the business model, firms can minimize their effort and expenditure of providing after sales support. Obviously, being ideal, the ideal Business model will not have any liability after sales.

(7) No fear on seasonality, perishability and price drop:

Many of conventional business firms are facing problems of season /non-season based business fluctuations, perished products with time and distance, and unexpected price drop due to competition, or decreased demand etc. In ideal business model, the products/services are chosen in such a way that there should not be problems like seasonality, perishability and price drop.

4. Challenges to Achieve Ideal Business

To realize the Ideal Business in practice, we need to identify a product or service which is intangible in nature. The business should be monopoly and controlled by any place in the world. The product/service and the business model should be chosen in such a way as it should have properties, at least close to Ideal Business properties. The decision on nature of product/service, the distribution channel and the business model plays an important role in realizing ideal business in practice.

5. Possible Solution through E-Business Model

An intangible product/service marketed through E-business model is the possible solution while approaching towards idealization of the business. A ubiquitous E-Business model using intangible product/service is most suitable for elevation to Ideal business. Most of the properties discussed in Fig. 1 of Ideal business can be compared to the properties of E-business using mobile devices. A block diagram of customer oriented E-business model using mobile device is shown in Fig. 6 [4].

In this model, based on user request, the mobile device identifies the user through physical possession of the device, passwords, or biometrics such as voice recognition (path 1). The mobile banking service provider authenticates the transaction request from the device via either subscriber identification (as with existing phones) or cryptographic mechanisms such as digital signatures or secure protocols, like the Wireless Transport Layer Security Specification through private network service provider PNSP (path 2). The users can perform secured operations on account balance or loan account statement, transfer money between two accounts in the same bank (internal transaction), loan payment, or payment of electricity, water, phone, credit card and cellular phone/pager bills, through the bank (path 3). The financial transaction can be also performed between the mobile banking service provider and the merchant for m-commerce payment through PNSP (path3a)and/ or other financial institution(s) for bill payments or interbank transfer through PNSP (path 3b) and may involve secure payment protocols such as Internet Keyed Payments/Secure Electronic Transactions, or iKP/SET [5]. After completion of requested transaction, the mobile banking service provider delivers a

confirmation of transaction to the user (path 4). In today's mobile phones, authorization is via subscriber identification mechanisms, which do not provide non-repudiation. However, in future, mobile consumers might also use a secure mobile signing device, to avoid disputes. This device may allow high-value transactions, as well as paying mobile operators who are not completely trusted (such as when roaming). Mobile communication mechanisms (such as GSM) allow the foreign (visited) network to authenticate the user with information from the home network. Charging requires prior agreements between the visited and the home networks. Designers of the Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS) recognized the difficulty of establishing agreements in advance among visited networks and all home networks [6]; thus, UMTS includes mechanisms for dynamic negotiation and setup of roaming agreements between a visited network and a home network. Roaming agreements seek to establish fees and ensure operator trustworthiness. Operators are trusted to deliver payments in time; foreign (remote) operators are also trusted to not overcharge visiting customers. A secure signing mobile device can prevent fraud (overcharging) by foreign network providers, thereby allowing more automated and variable roaming agreements. Operators can also use the final payments protocol [7], to extend pair-wise trust relationships into global trust relationships, allowing automated, secure, low-cost universal roaming.

Figure 6: Customer oriented E-business model using mobile device [4]

6. Mobile Business as an Ideal Business

A. Features of E-Business Using Mobile Devices

E-Business using mobile devices called mobile business, promises unlimited information, entertainment, and business, it gives users the ability to access the Internet from any location at any time, the capability to pinpoint an individual mobile terminal user's location, the functionality to access information at the point of need, and a need-based data/information update capability. Mobile business has features not available to traditional e-business, some of which are:

- 1) Ubiquity: Through mobile devices, business entities are able to reach customers anywhere at any time. On the other hand, users can also get any information they are

interested in, whenever they want regardless of where they are, through Internet-enabled mobile devices. In this sense, mobile business makes a service or an application available wherever and whenever such a need arises.

- 2) Personalization: An enormous number of information, services, and applications are currently available on the Internet, and the relevance of information users receive is of great importance. Since owners of mobile devices often require different sets of applications and services, mobile business applications can be personalized to represent information or provide services in ways appropriate to the specific user.
- 3) Flexibility: Because mobile devices are inherently portable, mobile users may be engaged in activities, such as meeting people or traveling, while conducting transactions or receiving information through their Internet-enabled mobile devices.
- 4) Dissemination: Some wireless infrastructures support simultaneous delivery of data to all mobile users within a specific geographical region. This functionality offers an efficient means to disseminate information to a large consumer population.

B. Mobile business Value Chain

Transport, basic enabling service, transaction support, presentation service, personalization support, user application, and content aggregators are the seven links in the mobile business value chain. The transport link maintains and operates the infrastructure and equipment to guarantee data communication between mobile users and application. Basic enabling service link provide services such as server hosting, data backup, and system integration. The Transaction support link provides the mechanism for assisting transactions, for security, and for billing users. The presentation service link converts the content of Internet-based applications to a wireless standard suitable for the screens of mobile devices. The Personalization support link gathers users' personal information, which enables personalized applications for individual users. The Content aggregators link provide information in a category or search facilities to help users find their way around the Internet. Finally the user applications link used to carry out mobile business transactions for mobile consumers. The following sectors will get benefit under m-business transformation [8]:

1. Banking industry: Possible facilities that could be offered include Account Balance Enquiries, Last 'n' transactions, Utility Bills Payment, Cheque clearing notifications, Inter account Transfers, Statement and Cheque book requests, Access to Portfolio management and other share dealing services.
2. Share market industry: Mobile phone-based stock trading allows users to receive instant updates on market information. The system allows to users to identify which stock they are interested in and what levels of alert they want. The warnings are then sent to the user's handset, and then they can buy or sell immediately without going to a computer.
3. Shopping: Many mobile service providers are planned to launch services that promote shopping using mobile. Fabmart, Zee marketing are few examples. Customers can pay for their purchases through their mobile phone bills. Text message shopping is already in use to buy books, CD etc., at bargain rate.

4. Building and construction materials industry: The fragmented nature, geographical spread and multiplicity of levels in the distribution structure for most products in this industry offers unique challenges and opportunities for e-business & m-business initiatives. M-business adaptation in this sector would be driven by factors such as improving brand building and customer services, penetrating markets in the semi-urban and rural pockets, improved dealer management, and ensuring timely supplies and services.
5. Metal industry: M-business adaptation in the metal sector would be primarily driven by working with lower inventories and adapting IT techniques and catering the customers through remote devices. This will increase market coverage and widen distribution reach, improved dealer management and controlling cost at every stage of the value chain. Metals, as commodity, also provide considerable scope for on-line tendering and auction applications.
6. Office automation industry: The Indian office automation industry is another potential candidate to adopt m-business strategies to its sales and service. The major benefits would be improved customer service, wider market coverage, and marketing and procurement costs reductions.
7. Packaging industry: The packing industry is another potential sector for adopting m-business. Handling order taking and order placement through mobile, the package industries can improve supply efficiency, customer service and market coverage.
8. Indian engineering industry: Engineering industry with huge annual turnover is another potential candidate for m-business implementation. Front-end activities like enhanced customer service and receiving new order, and back-end activities like enhanced vendor communication and booking purchases can emerge key priority areas in this industry.
9. Electrical and electronics industry: Implementing e-business and m-business in these industries is expected to result in improved sales and customer service through better information dissemination.
10. Chemical industry: Chemical and Petro-chemical industries are considered on-line business is a cost reduction tool. By adopting these strategies they would improve supply chain efficiency and reduce marketing / procurement costs.
11. Hotels and tourism industries: Booking hotel rooms and resorts at any time, at any place can be done through m-business options.
12. Pharmaceutical industry: Pharmaceutical industry views m-business as a tool that would aid community building, and to smaller extent, reduce costs through better supply chain management. They also expect to use this medium to provide people with more information on diseases and the products used to cure them.
13. Logistics industries: Both transportation and warehousing parts of logistics are potential candidates for m-business implementation due to the fact of increase in products sold on-line. The need to move a large volume of small parcels and the increase in customer expectations.
14. Auto-components industry: The auto-component industry is another prominent candidate for m-business implementation. Due to the increasing competition in the

domestic market and threat of imports, necessitating widening of market reach, and exploring export markets.

15. Lottery and Betting: All on-line lotteries and betting can accept the bets through the message delivered by SMS. The M-business technology allows not only mobile betting but also, using a mobile video-phone, be able to watch the actual race while moving on the road or while travelling in an aeroplane.
16. Mobile positioning services: With mobile positioning services your phone could become a personal tracking device, allowing your family friends and employer to know where you are at all times. Mobile positioning integrates with satellite positioning systems and let people tell others where they are.

C. Benefits of Mobile Business from Customers Point of view

The benefit from the customers' point of view is accessing services at anywhere, any time and any extent of time. These features significantly save the valuable time of the customer. The main advantages of m-business services for the customers are listed as follows:

- 1) **Ubiquity:** Through mobile devices, business applications are able to reach customers anywhere at any time. On the other hand, users can also get any information they are interested in, whenever they want regardless of where they are, through Internet-enabled mobile devices. In this sense, mobile business makes a service or an application available wherever and whenever such a need arises. Communication can take place independent of the users location. The advantages presented from the omnipresence of information and continual access to business will be exceptionally important to time-critical applications.
- 2) **Personalization:** An enormous number of business information, services, and applications are currently available on the Internet, and the relevance of information users receive is of great importance. Since owners of mobile devices often require different sets of applications and services, mobile business applications can be personalized to represent information or provide services in ways appropriate to the specific user. Additionally, personalized content is paramount in operating mobile devices because of the limitation of the user interface. Relevant information must always be only a single "click" away, since web access with any existing wireless device is not comparable to a PC screen either by size, resolution or "surfability". Therefore, subscriber profile ownerships is a key element in m-business success, as it will allow selectively targeted m-business applications. As such, the mobile database becomes a primary factor of m-business success by compiling personalized data bases and providing personalized services. One example, is the SIM (Subscriber Identification Module) smartcards which serve as a mobile database allowing the user to run applications and operate secure transactions. Such personalized information and transaction feeds, via mobile devices, offer the greatest potential for the customization necessary for long-term success.
- 3) **Reduced costs:** This is due to availing and using various products and services by number of customers online. The transaction fee charged by banking service providers

for financial services is much cheaper than conventional retail banking transaction fees. The heavy competition and the price war between mobile service providers also reduced mobile service usage cost.

- 4) **Flexibility:** Because mobile devices are inherently portable, mobile users may be engaged in activities, such as meeting people or traveling, while doing business, conducting transactions, or receiving information through their Internet-enabled mobile devices.
- 5) **Increased comfort:** Many customers secretly hate their business service provider/banks because of punitive charges, inconvenient opening hours and unhelpful branch staff. In mobile business due to quick and continuous access, purchases and transactions can be made 24 hours a day, without requiring the physical interaction with the service provider.
- 6) **Time saving:** The main benefit from the mobile business customers' point of view is significant saving of time by the automation of purchasing & banking services processing and introduction of an easy maintenance tools for managing customer's money. Since the response of the medium is very fast, the customer can wait till the last minute before purchasing and concluding a fund transfer.
- 7) **Convenience:** The ability and accessibility provided from wireless devices will further allow m-business to differentiate its abilities from conventional business and e-business. People will no longer be constrained by time or place in conducting business activities. Rather, m-business could be accessed in a manner which may eliminate some of the labor of life's activities. For example, consumers waiting in line or stuck in traffic will be able to handle daily transactions/purchases through m-business applications. Consumers may recognize a special comfort which could translate into an improved quality of life.
- 8) **Better cash management:** Mobile business facilities speed-up cash cycle and increases efficiency of business processes as large variety of cash management instruments are available on internet sites of banks. For example, it is possible to manage companies short term cash via online or mobile banking like investments in over-night, short and long term deposits, in commercial papers, in bonds and equities, in money market funds etc. In mobile business, customers can download the features of product/services or their history of different accounts and do a what-if analysis on their own mobile device, before affecting any transaction on the web or through mobile service providers. This will lead to better funds management.

D. Comparison of Mobile Business Properties with that of Ideal Business

The system properties like - free from Government regulations, portability, and satisfying our intellectual needs, availability of free time, independency of income with personal output, no liability after sales, and no headache like problems of seasonality, perishability and price drop; the market conditions like - unlimited global market, inelastic demand, and copyright/patenting opportunities of ideal business also can be realizable using mobile business properties for intangible products/services.

The input properties like - minimal labor requirements, low overhead, and low capital requirement; the output conditions like – high efficiency, and sustainable for long time, of ideal business also realizable to certain extent using mobile business properties for intangible products/services as shown in Table 1. Thus e-business using mobile devices called mobile business is a suitable business model for profit maximization and approaches to hypothetical ideal business model.

Table 1: Comparison of conventional business and online business in terms of ideal business characteristics

S. No.	Ideal Business Characteristics	Conventional Business	Online Business
1	The Ideal Business sells its products/services to the entire world and hence it has an unlimited global market.	No	Yes
2	The Ideal Business offers a product/service, which enjoys an inelastic demand.	No	Yes
3	The Ideal Business sells a product/service that cannot be easily copied. i.e., it is something that can be copyrighted or patented.	No	Yes
4	The Ideal Business has minimal labor requirements.	No	Yes
5	The Ideal Business operates on a low overhead.	No	Yes
6	The Ideal Business does not require big cash outlays or major investments in equipment or product.	No	Yes
7	The Ideal Business is relatively free of all kinds of government regulations or restrictions.	No	Yes
8	The Ideal Business is portable or easily moveable.	No	Yes
9	The Ideal Business satisfies your intellectual needs.	No	Yes
10	The Ideal Business leaves you with free time.	No	Yes
11	The Ideal Business is one in which your income is not limited by your personal output (Leverage).	No	Yes
12	The ideal Business will not have any liability after sales.	No	Yes
13	The ideal Business will not have problems like seasonality, perishability and price drop	No	Yes
14	In ideal Business the demand is always very high than supply and the efficiency of production is always 100%.	No	Yes
15	The ideal Business will be sustainable for long time.	No	Yes

E. Analysis of some possible Products/ Services for Ideal Business

Mobile business using various mobile devices for some of the products/services is suitable candidate for having ideal business characteristics. The products/services which are intangibles in nature used in mobile business transactions are most suitable candidates to follow almost all the characteristics of an ideal business model. Small business of selling the software products, e-books, e-music or any similar product/service will give the advantages of the Ideal Business properties. Like the possibility of ideal technology

concepts realization using nanotechnology [9], ideal business can be realized using e-business model called m-business.

7. Conclusion

- 1) The various properties of Ideal business are identified, classified and analysed.
- 2) A suitable business model is identified to realize most of the properties of Ideal Business.
- 3) Various E-business models are used to study the possibility of realization of Ideal Business.
- 4) It is found that ubiquitous E-Business called mobile business with intangible product/service has most of the Ideal business properties.

References

- [1] P. S. Aithal and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, Ideal education system and its realization through online education model using mobile devices, Proceedings of IISRO Multi Conference 2014, Bangkok, 7/01/2014, ISBN No. 978-81-927104-33-13, pp. 140 - 146, 2014.
- [2] E. M. Rogers, 'Diffusion of Innovation', The Free Press, NY, 1995.
- [3] R. M. Morgan, and S. D. Hunt, 'The commitment-trust theory of relationship marketing', Journal of Marketing, Vol. 58, (July), pp. 20–38, 1994.
- [4] K. V. M. Varambally & P. S. Aithal, "Mobile Business Technology and Business Proliferation of Banks - A Futuristic Approach" Amity Business Review, vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 9 – 25, January – June, 2009.
- [5] R. MacGregor, C. Ezvan, and L. Liquori, "Secure Electronic Transactions: Credit Card Payment on the Web in Theory and Practice," SG24- 4978-00 Redbook, IBM, International Technical support Organization, Raleigh, NC, July 2, 1997; see www.redbooks.ibm.com/
- [6] G. Horn, and B. Preneel, "Authentication and payment in future mobile systems," In Proceedings of the European symposium on Research in Computer Security (ESORICS'98) Lecture notes in Computer Science (Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, Sept.6-8), Springer Verlag, pp. 277-293, 1998.
- [7] A. Herzberg, "Payments and banking with mobile personal devices," Communications of the ACM, vol. 46, No.5, pp. 53-58, 2003.
- [8] P. S. Aithal and K.V. M. Varambally, "Security Issues in Online Financial Transactions with Special Reference to Banking Industry," In Quality in Service Sector and Managerial Challenges-Allied Publisher Pvt. Ltd. 2006, ISBN:81-7764-992-2, pp. 103-114, 2006.
- [9] P. S. Aithal and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, Ideal Technology Concept & its Realization Opportunity using Nanotechnology, International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEEM), Volume 4, Issue 2, pp. 1 - 12, February 2015.

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